

Community Review: Research Software Engineers Australia and New Zealand (RSE-AUNZ)

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CONTENTS

CONTENTS	1
<u>INTRODUCTION TO SURVEY REPORT</u>	<u>2</u>
RSE-AUNZ INTRODUCTION	2
<u>ALIGNMENT WITH ARDC CORE ACTIVITIES AND STRATEGY</u>	<u>3</u>
<u>RELATED COMMUNITIES</u>	<u>3</u>
SURVEY RESULTS: SECTOR NEED, INTEREST AND INVOLVEMENT	3
PURPOSE	4
INVOLVEMENT	4
INTEREST	5
BENEFITS THAT THE COMMUNITY HAS DELIVERED	6
<u>COSTS OF RUNNING THE COMMUNITY</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>WAYS TO IMPROVE THE RUNNING OF THE COMMUNITY</u>	<u>9</u>
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	9
<u>FUTURE OF COMMUNITY LEADERSHIP</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>APPENDIX 1: RESULTS OF COMMUNITY SURVEY</u>	<u>11</u>
<u>APPENDIX 2: RESULTS OF STEERING COMMITTEE SURVEY</u>	<u>11</u>

INTRODUCTION TO SURVEY REPORT

This report presents a summary of the results obtained from both the anonymous community survey and the steering committee survey conducted by the ARDC lead in April 2023. The primary purpose of this document is to provide an informed recommendation on the continuation of the community, outlining comments and suggestions from the community regarding the specific format in which the community should proceed.

The evaluation presented herein aligns with the [ARDC Communities Strategy](#) (ARDC private documentation).

RSE-AUNZ INTRODUCTION

“A Research Software Engineer (RSE) combines professional software engineering expertise with an intimate understanding of research” (rse-aunz.org). Around the world there is an increasing awareness of the value RSEs provide to the research community and many research-based organisations are working towards having the RSE role recognised and defined as a career path in its own right.

The Research Software Engineer (RSE) Australia and New Zealand (AUNZ) Community was formally established in 2018 to support RSE’s in New Zealand and Australia by raising awareness, advocating for RSE’s and providing RSE’s opportunities to connect through networking, information sharing, events, etc. The RSE-AUNZ is a community of practice whose aim is to bring together a defined group of practitioners to share expertise, knowledge, and learn from each other, improving their practice, thereby growing the capability in the sector. Membership is open and free, by subscribing to the mailing list rse-aunz.org. It has been an active community since 2018 with healthy growth. Currently the RSE-AUNZ mailing list has 423 members (May 09, 2023). Membership growth per quarter is shared in the [about page](#), with 123 new members in the last year.

Over the last year (2022-2023) while adapting to life post pandemic, the [steering committee](#) recognised an opportunity to create intentional goals, direction and focus for community activities and support to make the most of the limited resources we have. The committee has worked on putting together a strategy which clearly defines goals and key results for the upcoming years. [This strategy](#) (2023-2025) document is published on Figshare.

This community is co-facilitated by [volunteers](#) and has support from two international organisations the [ARDC](#) and [NeSI](#). The community is aimed at four stakeholders: researchers and academics who develop and maintain code, those who bring communities together across the research and technical domains, software engineers who work in the research domain, and systems administrators who maintain research systems.

ALIGNMENT WITH ARDC CORE ACTIVITIES AND STRATEGY

The RSE-AUNZ community is specifically mentioned in the implementation plan, under the Software Program, [sustain research software project](#).

RELATED COMMUNITIES

The members and the steering committee of the RSE-AUNZ identified a few communities with small overlap, such as:

- "third spacer" communities (events such as, 2 webinars in 2020: [1](#), [2](#) and a lunch [3](#) in 2018)
- Australian HPC sysadmins Slack <https://australianhpc.slack.com> ongoing

Also, it was mentioned that it's possible that most domains have similar groups to the RSE-AUNZ. For example,

- Astronomy, ANITA the [Australian National Institute for Theoretical Astrophysics](#), a virtual institute which aims to raise the profile of Australian theoretical astrophysics, <https://anita.edu.au>.
- Bioinformatics [ABACBS](#) the Australian Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Society Inc. and [COMBINE](#), a student-run Australian organisation for students in computational biology, bioinformatics, and related fields. COMBINE is the student subcommittee of [ABACBS](#) as well as the official [International Society for Computational Biology \(ISCB\)](#) Regional Student Group (RSG) for Australia.

There also might be institutional or regional RSE chapters, these are encouraged by the RSE-AUNZ community to become independent in meeting and suggesting smaller projects for the community. From March 2023 there is an [open call for regional coordinators](#).

SURVEY RESULTS: SECTOR NEED, INTEREST AND INVOLVEMENT

We received 29 responses to the community survey (6.8% of members subscribed to the mailing list) plus 3 responses from the steering committee.

PURPOSE

This community aims to build awareness of the diverse Research Software Engineer (RSE) roles, to connect those in the RSE domain, and to help build practical solutions for the RSE community. Of received responses, 58.6 % (17) agreed or strongly agreed that the community meets its purpose. It is important to notice that 20.6 % (6) a fifth of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with this question. Out of this 20.6% there is strong correlation with those who felt the community is unwelcoming, however further evaluation is needed to identify the reason behind this response.

The community meets its purpose

29 responses

INVOLVEMENT

About a quarter of respondents 27.5% (8) agreed or strongly agreed with the statement “I actively participate in this community”. A larger percentage 41.4% (12) responded “neutral”, and 31 % (9) do not actively participate in the community. This likely reflects the past participation model promoted in the community; until 2022 this community served to disseminate news (transmissive). Where the members of the community engaged by consuming information, shared via the mailing list, and participating in a few events that convey information. The goal until very recently was to inform and inspire the community.

With the new [Community Strategy](#) the steering committee is transitioning to encourage members to contribute and collaborate in projects they see of benefit to the community. The steering committee is now actively calling for volunteers to be involved in short term goals that contribute to the strategy. Promoting a more cooperative model that is open to receive feedback and achieve common goals.

I actively participate in this community

29 responses

INTEREST

There is strong interest in the community expressed by members. This is demonstrated by the [community's continued growth](#), active engagement in frequent [discussions](#) via the mailing list and consistent participation in [community-organised events](#).

The support from ARDC in the steering committee, to grow the community, coordinate events and disseminate news is appropriate and appreciated by the community. The support from NeSI to support the steering committee activities and organise the RSE tech talks is relevant to keep frequent activities to meet the membership. In addition, the support from volunteers as part of the steering committee and those who support activities is *invaluable* for the continuation of this community.

More than half of respondents 62% (18) agreed or strongly agreed with the statement "I feel welcome and included in the community". Furthermore, while the examples of community participation mentioned above indicate a positive level of engagement, it is important to acknowledge that 20.7% (6) of respondents felt neutral about this statement and 17.2% (5) of respondents disagree or strongly disagree with the statement. By proactively addressing these concerns, a stronger sense of belonging could be achieved.

I feel welcome and included in the community

29 responses

BENEFITS THAT THE COMMUNITY HAS DELIVERED

The majority of respondents 51.7% (15) agreed or strongly agreed “the community is useful for me”. The most frequently selected sources of value provided by the group were 67.9% “networking”, 64.3% “sharing information”, followed by 46.4% “the collaborative platform it provides, e.g. mailing list, events”.

The community is useful for me

29 responses

What has been a key value for you that the community brings?

28 responses

Some of the RSE-AUNZ outcomes identified by the steering committee are:

- New initiatives for networking locally, now that we are returning to in-person events, and more volunteers are participating to coordinate, reference: <https://rse-aunz.github.io/2023/03/25/Ongoing-Meetup-Events.html>
- Many members have also expressed their support and excitement about the new Research Software Awards sponsored by the ARDC, and targeted to this community.", reference: <https://ardc.edu.au/get-involved/ardc-sponsored-awards-and-prizes/>
- We have demonstrated the value of the community by getting partners to contribute in kind and financially to the community, reference: <https://rse-aunz.github.io/assets/2023%20RSE%20Asia%20Australia%20Prospectus.pdf>
- The International RSE survey 2022 has been cited multiple times, reference: <https://zenodo.org/record/7015772>
- The RSE-AUNZ Strategy 2023-2025 has been shared with the community, received feedback and it [is published on Figshare](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21385392.v2), reference: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21385392.v2>
- The first RSE unconference in Australia Asia 2022, improved and boosted networking within community members. Ref: <https://rse-aunz.github.io/2022-Asia-Australia-unconference/> a new unconference for 2023 is being planned, reference: <https://rse-aunz.github.io/2023-Asia-Australia-unconference/>

These outputs can be discovered by multiple [communication channels](#):

Where can any outputs be discovered?

3 responses

COSTS OF RUNNING THE COMMUNITY

Running the community is mainly led by volunteer's time, who are either part of the steering committee or volunteer for a specific activity.

In 2022, the steering committee organised the first unconference in Australia in collaboration with [RSE Asia](#). This event received sponsorship to support it and also charged a low fee for participation. This helped collect funds to invest within the community. One of the first covered costs was an optional honorarium for volunteers helping in the organising committee. Bursaries for people to attend for free were available and 10% of the earnings of the event went to "[Pay the rent](#)", a grassroots collective of First Nations people.

The RSE-AUNZ also receives in kind support from two international organisations the ARDC and NeSI, each providing time for one of the steering committees members. ARDC invests approximately 80 hours of ARDC time per year in the RSE-AUNZ. The ARDC has also contributed financially to running the community, by sponsoring events and providing the online platform access (zoom events) to run the [2022 RSEAA unconference](#).

In addition to the aforementioned and regular time contributions. Participation in the community is relatively low-effort for members, with most 78.6% ($\frac{2}{3}$ or 22) indicating that they invest up to 8 hours per year on participation.

How much time do you invest in the community?

28 responses

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE RUNNING OF THE COMMUNITY

The survey respondents added four comments suggesting how to improve the communication channels of the community:

- “I would like community members to provide more input on communication and sharing what is available to them, such as events, guides, workshops, etc”
- “discord, mailing list and funded local catch ups”
- “A 'permanent' virtual community presence”
- “I would like to see more sessions and discussions. The idea of having regular meetings with tech talks like sessions for RSE-AUNZ will be valuable. Bringing up suggestions on how the EU and US are valuing RSEs with some guest speakers would be on my wish list”

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

A range of communication channels are used for the RSE-AUNZ community. The main communication channel with the public is the website (rse-aunz.org). The main communication channel among members is the [mailing list](#), available to those who subscribe to it (for free). Members are able to post to the mailing list and are encouraged to do so, by sharing news, events, jobs, questions or answers. The frequency of posts vary between 2 and 11 every month, in the last half year. Additional communication channels managed by the community are: the RSE-AUNZ twitter account ([@rse_aunz](#)), the [RSE-AUNZ LinkedIn Group](#), and the recently created [RSE-AUNZ eventbrite profile](#). There are external communication channels from our supporting institutions such as: ARDC comms channels (newsletter and social media posts) and NeSI (newsletter and eventbrite profile) which amplify our community efforts.

FUTURE OF COMMUNITY LEADERSHIP

The RSE-AUNZ is overseen by a [steering committee](#) which is elected by the members. The current committee is as follows:

Two co-Chairs: Nooriyah Poonawala-Lohani and Manodeep Sinha, and three general steering committee members: Rowland Mosbergen, Paula Andrea Martinez and Janet Stacey. The steering committee attends monthly meetings, and extra meetings when necessary, to discuss the running of the group and suggest next actions. Each steering committee member has equal voting rights to select which activities to support and lead. Each new activity must be approved by the majority of the steering committee members and have at least one person leading the effort.

From the steering committee members 2 out of 5 are likely to step down in the future. One of the steering committee members emphasised “I would like to recruit more folks to the steering committee - get fresh enthusiasm and ideas, and pass on the leadership baton”. Since last year, the steering committee has proactively recruited volunteers for smaller projects run by the community. Nonetheless, a call for new steering committee members is open and should take place via elections as in previous years.

ARDC is not the primary facilitator of this community group and it would be very likely the group continues without ARDC taking a leading role, but offering continuous support in other ways such as in kind time or financial support.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE

This community aims to build awareness of the diverse Research Software Engineer (RSE) roles, to connect those in the RSE domain, and to help build practical solutions for the RSE community. Given the most recent change to encourage community led activities, and having strong support from members and sponsors it is recommended that the group continue in its present format.

In addition, members have provided comments and questions about recommendations for the future (some added text in *italics*):

- “Looking forward to more volunteers in the community”
- “merch? a better and more informative website?”
- “Somehow get more widespread in the organisations, be the central place for discussions about RSE, maybe host/promote *open source software* (OSS) projects and initiatives within AUS/NZ, and overseas. And it would be really great if it pushed for more adoption of Open Standards that already exist, and for tools and integration with tools that already exist (instead of re-creating platforms/services/tools/companies/groups in AUS/NZ)”
- “The AU/NZ organisation is overly focused on promoting diversity inclusion. It has lost momentum and is going backwards. It should be dissolved and reconstituted as state-based organisations that put recruiting and supporting actual RSEs as its prime objective.”

- “Can't really comment. I've had too much on my plate for a few years & haven't interacted with the group. Problem 2: I'm currently not in academia, so I don't really have justification for substantial involvement (unless I return).”
- “Funding for local/regional events”
- “What I need is a group that lobbies universities for fair pay. What I don't have is time. Maybe this group isn't that and that would be fair.”
- “Focus on two areas: 1) Improved research sector level recognition of career paths; 2) a discussion of ideas, projects, and good practice that make up day-to-day work across sectors. The current inward focus of the community makes it unwelcoming as it's difficult to focus on what members have in common.”
- “Any engagements which help the RSE cause *are* welcome. Creating a wish list as done through the RSE conference was great. Perhaps put some actions to help the cause. Can a RSE Working Group create an impact?”
- “I think it's just going to take time to build more mass.”
- “We're RSEs, could we use our technical skills to work together, building our platform?”

Members and steering committee, It is time to reflect on the survey responses and suggestions to improve the community. It would be interesting to investigate more into engagement, as why so few responses were received and if it reflects the feedback of the overall community.

APPENDIX 1: RESULTS OF COMMUNITY SURVEY

View the [anonymous community survey responses](#).

APPENDIX 2: RESULTS OF STEERING COMMITTEE SURVEY

View the [anonymous steering committee responses](#).